

Multidimensional Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Business : It's Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract : *A number of intelligence products and services have been emerging during recent years, which have commercial utility and their socio-economic impact. The question arises whether AI really have the potential to transform the world or it just only a hype. In the present business scenario Artificial Intelligence is transforming the business world at a rapid pace. AI have been used in various sectors like healthcare, transport, agriculture, education, e-commerce, entertainment, finance gaming and many more. AI has resulted in increased operating efficiency, maximization in production and profitability, cost saving, time saving and quick decision-making. This paper examines the Artificial Intelligence (AI's) impact in the business taking full-time employees from various natures in the state of Bihar. Primary data has been collected through online survey and personal visit to the organization. Significant Artificial Intelligence's (AI's) impact on business has been measured considering four key variables. Artificial Intelligence's (AI's) impact on operational efficiency, cyber security, customer satisfaction, and predictive analysis in the business has been analyzed. The study concludes that there is a positive Artificial Intelligence (AI) on operational efficiency, cyber security, customer satisfaction, and predictive analysis in the business.*

Keywords : AI Innovations, Operational Efficiency, Cyber Security.

Introduction

In the world of business, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force. It has brought a revolution in the digital world. Although the work is performed by AI very effectively & efficiently it cannot replace humans. In India, the Adoption of AI in different sectors is at the initial stage but companies have been adopting AI gradually to perform the job. It is creating

competition in the market. It is used in different functional areas of companies like marketing, sales, finance, and production. In addition to functional jobs, it can transform businesses through creative ideas. It provides solutions for challenging tasks, which aids in the rapid expansion of businesses. From routine work to analytical work, all these are performed by AI.

The Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Business

- (a) **Financial Tasks** : By evaluating past data and finding trends that might estimate future financial performance; AI enhances financial forecasting and assists organizations with strategic planning, forecasting, and budgeting. AI monitors financial transactions, it protects from fraudulent and suspicious transactions.
- (b) **Customer Support** : Earlier customer executives used to handle customer calls and customer support. AI replaces Customer executive job.. Handling inquiries, providing customer support 24*7 basis and managing basic tasks are performed by AI-driven chatbots and virtual assistants.. This has resulted in improved customer service and satisfaction and reduced operational costs.
- (c) **Customer Analytics** : Market and customer-related insights are taken by AI by processing customer data. Customers' needs, changing purchase patterns, customer feedback, behaviour, and product preference are analysed which helps in marketing and product recommendations.
- (d) **Data Interpretation and Analysis** : It is a core function of AI. AI algorithms help businesses with demand forecasting, inventory management, and strategic planning by analyzing past data to forecast future trends.
- (e) **Detection and prevention from cyber threats** : Using the vast set of data it identifies possible threats, developing new algorithms to protect from cyber attacks of our digital assets and belongings.

Challenges of using AI in Business

As I have discussed a numerous benefits of using AI in business. However, it has some challenges which restrict the effective and successful adoption of AI in the business, which are as bellows.

- (i) **Data Related Challenges** : The resulting output is depending on the quality of the data. Accurate data have a accurate result and inaccurate data have a inaccurate result. To get a desire task it requires a vast amount of qualitative

and quantitative data. However, obtaining, gathering, and preserving the required data is a challenging job to the enterprise. Inadequate, erroneous, or out-of-date data can result in inaccurate outcomes and wrong decision.

- (ii) **Shortage of AI Professional** : Lack of AI skilled professional including machine learning expert, AI engineers, and data scientists are the second challenge of AI adoption in business. Implementing and managing AI initiatives effectively hampered by a lack of internal expertise. Training of existing employee is time taking and costly procedure.
- (iii) **Cost related Issues** : Investment in AI infrastructure, hiring AI professional, purchasing software and hard ware, annual maintenance charges, renewal of software and license Aids in business cost. Bearing these cost is challenging to the small businesses.
- (iv) **Complexity in Integration with existing System** : It can be difficult to integrate AI into an existing IT infrastructure, especially if the systems are antiquated or not made to accommodate AI. Implementation of AI requires modification, improvement in the existing system. Sometimes it cause disruption in the business process and necessitate a time of adjustment.
- (v) **Regulatory Compliance** : Adoption of AI in business requires compliance of various legal procedures. Laws and regulations vary by industry and region. Information technology Act, 2000, Personal Data Protection Bill (PDPB) and Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, For financial work RBI guidelines to be followed regarding data security, customer protection, and risk management, SEBI guidelines, patent laws, The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare for health, The Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY) for manufacturing and smart cities.

Literature Review

- **Enholm, I. M., et al. (2022)** analyzed in their study that Artificial intelligence (AI) comprised of a broad range of technologies that provide businesses several benefits in the form of increased economic value. In order to gain business value organizations moving towards AI. However, businesses are still facing difficulties in adopting, using, integrating AI's in daily operations.
- **Budhwar, P et al. (2022)**, In their study they analyzed various AI driven application like Bio metrics, speech recognition, sensors, chatbot, Chat GPT, Internet of Things (IOT), mobile technology, gig technology, geo-tagging.

These things have increased revolution in industrial concern. AI have been used in human resource management, for managing the employees, recruiting the personnel, and decision making.

- **Jain, R. (2023)**, focuses the Artificial Intelligence (AI) in business and found the multidimensional significant impact on business performance, increased productivity, cost reduction, smooth business operation, quick decision making, Adoption of AI, however, is not without its difficulties. These include issues about data security and privacy, moral issues, and possible employment displacement.
- **Bharadiya, J. P. (2023)** explores in the study that, AI helps examining customer purchase pattern, survey feedback of the customer satisfaction, browsing behavior at various online shopping platforms, This boosts customer happiness and revenue growth by helping firms take advantage of cross-selling and up selling opportunities.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the Artificial Intelligence's (AI's) impact on business operations including operational efficiency and business innovations.
- To analyse the future growth of AI.

Research Methodology

The study is conducted on 100 respondents in the Bihar state. Respondents comprised of full time employees from various nature of organizations representatives like finance, manufacturing, technology and customers. Significant Artificial Intelligence's (AI's) impact on business has been measured considering four key variables. These variables are AI's impact on the operational efficiency, cyber security, customer satisfaction, Predictive analysis. Data has been collected through online mode and personal interviews with the respondents to know the AI's impacts, its current adoptions and future of AI in the business.

Data Interpretation

Reliability Test

Values of Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Respondents
.897	100

Source : Test based on questionnaire.

A reliability test was conducted to know the reliability of data. It is calculated on 100 respondents and found Cronbach's Alpha value .897. This value confirms good representation of quality data and considered reliable for the study.

Table-1 : Gender Wise Frequency of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	% of participation
Male	67	67%
Female	33	33%
Total	100	100%

Source: Compilation from questionnaire

Table no.1 exhibits that out of 100 respondents, 67 were male and 33 were female. The number of male respondents was found more than the female.

Table-2 : Frequency of Respondents on AI's Impact on the Operational Efficiency of the Business

	Very High Impact	High Impact	Medium Impact	Low Impact	No Impact	Total
Frequency	54	23	13	7	3	100

Source: Compilation from questionnaire

Table no2 depicts respondent's responses on AI's Impact on operational efficiency on business. Majority of the respondents opinioned very high impact, 23% opinioned high impact, 7 respondents low impact and only 3 respondent's opinioned no AI's Impact on operational efficiency on the business.

Table-3 : Frequency of Respondents on AI's Impact on the Cyber Security

	Very High Impact	High Impact	Medium Impact	Low Impact	No Impact	Total
Frequency	54	24	10	7	5	100

Source: Compilation from questionnaire

Respondent's frequency on AI's impact on the cyber security presented in Table no 3. Out of 100 respondent 54 favoring very high impact, while 24 favored high impact, only 7 respondents favored low impact. The number of favoring no impact is very low.

Table-4 : Frequency of Respondents on AI's Impact on Customer Satisfaction

	Very High Impact	High Impact	Medium Impact	Low Impact	No Impact	Total
Frequency	60	22	8	5	5	100

Source: Compilation from questionnaire

Frequency of Respondents on AI's impact on customer satisfaction is recorded in Table 4. 60% respondent's satisfaction level is very high, 22% showed high satisfaction level, 8% medium satisfied, five percent respondents low satisfied and only 5% respondents have no satisfaction.

Table-5 : Frequency of Respondents on AI's Impact on Predictive Analysis

	Very High Impact	High Impact	Medium Impact	Low Impact	No Impact	Total
Frequency	64	21	7	3	5	100

Source: Compilation from questionnaire

Table no 5 depicts the representation of the respondents on AI's impact on predictive analysis. Only 3 respondents argued that there is low AI's impact on predictive analysis, 64 respondents strongly favored, 21 respondent favoring high impact, the number of favoring low impact respondent's are less than the respondents favoring no impact.

Hypothesis

H₀₁ : There is no significant AI's impact on the operational efficiency of the business.

H₁ : There is a significant AI's impact on the operational efficiency of the business.

Table-6 : Testing of Hypothesis 1 by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	140.286	4.000	35.071	7.967	0.000	2.466
Within Groups	422.625	96.000	4.402			
Total	562.911	100.000				

Interpretation : Calculated F value 7.967 is greater than the Critical value at 5 percent level of significance 2.466 Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative Hypothesis (H1) is accepted, confirming that There is significant AI's impact on the operational efficiency of the business.

H₀₂ : There is no significant AI's impact on the cyber security.

H₂ : There is significant AI's impact on the cyber security.

Table-7 : Testing of Hypothesis 2 by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	155.015	4	38.753	8.71	0.00	2.47
Within Groups	422.625	95	4.448			
Total	577.64	99				

Interpretation : Calculated F value 8.71 > the Critical value at 5 percent level of significance 2.47. Hence, null hypothesis (H₀₂) is rejected and alternative Hypothesis (H₂) is accepted, confirming that there is significant AI's impact on the cyber security.

H₀₃ : There is no significant AI's impact on customer satisfaction.

H₃ : There is significant AI's impact on customer satisfaction.

Table-8 : Testing of Hypothesis 3 by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	148.769	4.000	37.192	10.254	0.000	2.467
Within Groups	344.591	95.000	3.627			
Total	493.360	99.000				

Interpretation : Calculated F value $10.254 >$ the Critical value at 5 percent level of significance 2.46. There is a significant difference between mean square of two groups. Hence, null hypothesis (H_{03}) is rejected and alternative Hypothesis (H_3) is accepted, confirming that there is significant AI's impact on customer satisfaction.

H_{04} : There is no significant AI's impact on Predictive analysis.

H_4 : There is significant AI's impact on Predictive analysis.

Table-9 : Testing of Hypothesis 4 by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	140.189	4.000	35.047	10.790	0.000	2.467
Within Groups	308.571	95.000	3.248			
Total	448.760	99.000				

Interpretation : Calculated F value $10.790 >$ the Critical value at 5 percent level of significance 2.467. There is a significant difference between mean square of two groups. Hence, null hypothesis (H_{04}) is rejected and alternative Hypothesis (H_4) is accepted, confirming that there is significant AI's impact on Predictive analysis.

Conclusions

On the basis of literature review and result of the hypotheses it is concluded that adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI's) in the business have been increasing and it has brought digital revolution in the business environment. There is a significant impact on the operational efficiency, enhanced cyber security, improved customer satisfaction and helpful in data interpretation and predictive analysis in the business.

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